

Impact of Different Micro-nutrient Grades on Biological Properties of French Bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris* L.) Growing Soil

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Abstract

A field experiment was carried out at research farm of Department of Soil Science, College of Agriculture, Vasant Rao Naik Marathwada Krishi Vidyapeeth, Parbhani, Maharashtra during Rabi season of 2024-2025 to optimize nutrient-management practices through foliar feeding in 'Phule Vijaya' variety of french bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris* L.) The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with ten treatments viz, Absolute control, RDF (As per crop), RDF+ Grade-1(a) @ 25kg ha⁻¹ (Gypsum based), RDF+ Grade-1(b) @ 25kg ha⁻¹ (Bentonite based), RDF+ Govt. notified Grade 1(c) @ 25kg ha⁻¹ (Gypsum based), RDF+Grade-II (a) @ 0.5 and 1% (Chelation with EDTA), RDF+ Grade-II (b) @ 0.5 and 1% (Chelation with glycine), RDF+ Grade-II (c) 0.5 and 1% (Chelation with EDTA), RDF+ Grade-II (d) 0.5 and 1% (Chelation with citric acid) and RDF+ Govt. notified Grade-II (e) @ 0.5 and 1% (Chelation with EDTA). The study revealed that application of RDF+ Grade-1(a) @ 25kg ha⁻¹ (Gypsum based) was resulted in higher microbial population including bacteria (41.73 CFU×10⁻⁷), fungi (6.55 CFU×10⁻⁴) and actinomycetes (43.43 CFU×10⁻⁵). Whereas, significantly higher dehydrogenase activity (48.12 g TPF 24 hr⁻¹ g⁻¹ soil), acid phosphatase activity (53.11 g p-NP g⁻¹ soil hr⁻¹) and alkaline phosphatase activity (65.49 g p-NP g⁻¹ soil hr⁻¹) in soil were observed at harvest stage of french bean with same treatment.

(Key words): French bean, micronutrient grades, soil microbes, soil enzymes)

Introduction

French bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris* L.) is a globally significant food legume, providing essential protein, vitamins and minerals to over 300 million people worldwide. Despite its importance, the productivity of french bean is often constrained by low soil fertility and poor

nutrient management practices, particularly regarding micronutrients. While macronutrients (nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium) are essential in large quantities, micronutrients such as zinc (Zn), iron (Fe), manganese (Mn), copper (Cu), and boron (B) are required in smaller amounts but play critical roles as components

or cofactors in various plant enzymatic and metabolic processes, including photosynthesis, respiration, and nitrogen fixation.

Soil biological properties, such as microbial biomass, enzyme activities, and organic carbon content, are vital indicators of soil health and quality, playing a pivotal role in nutrient cycling and overall ecosystem sustainability. The integrated use of organic and inorganic fertilizers has been shown to improve soil physical properties and nutrient availability, which in turn promotes microbial activity and beneficial interactions like biological nitrogen fixation. Dehydrogenase is an intracellular enzyme present in all living microbial cells that is closely linked to microbial respiratory activities. As a result, it is considered a reliable indicator of overall microbial activity. The enzyme facilitates the conversion of protons and electrons from substrates to acceptors, which leads to the oxidation of soil organic materials. These processes are integral to respiration and are utilized by soil microorganisms, with their efficiency being influenced by the soil type. The activity of acid phosphatase is predominating in acid soil and predominantly due to plants. There is a strong correlation between pH and phosphatase activity. However, the majority of acid phosphatase originates from associated fungal and plants. The nutritional state of the plant would have a greater impact on acid phosphatase activity.

This study aims to evaluate the effect of various micronutrient grades on the biological properties of soil at the harvest stage of french bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris* L.). The research seeks to identify the optimal micronutrient grade and application rate that not only enhances crop performance but also maintains or improves long-term soil health and fertility.

Materials and Methods

A field experiment was conducted at research farm of Department of Soil Science, College of Agriculture, Vasant Rao Naik Marathwada Krishi Vidyapeeth, Parbhani, Maharashtra. The

experimental soil was clayey in texture, calcareous in nature, moderately alkaline, low in organic carbon (3.27 g kg^{-1}), available nitrogen ($131.98 \text{ kg ha}^{-1}$), available phosphorous (11.86 kg ha^{-1}), high in available potassium ($711.78 \text{ kg ha}^{-1}$), sufficient in available sulphur (10.12 kg ha^{-1}), deficient in DTPA zinc (0.68 mg kg^{-1}), DTPA iron (4.75 mg kg^{-1}), DTPA copper (1.33 mg kg^{-1}), DTPA manganese (2.58 mg kg^{-1}) and available boron (0.33 mg kg^{-1}). The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with ten treatments. The recommended dose of fertilizer is 120:60:60 NPK kg ha^{-1} was applied. The half dose of N along with full dose of P and K was applied as basal and remaining half dose of N is applied as top dressing on 30 days after sowing.

In the present investigation different micronutrient formulations were prepared as per the nutrient standards mentioned in the table 1. The soil micronutrient formulations Grade-I (a) gypsum and Grade-I (b) bentonite based contains, Zn: 6 %, Fe: 5%, Mn: 1 %, B: 1 % and Cu: 0.5 %. The micronutrient formulation Govt. notified Grade-I (c) gypsum based was prepared as per Maharashtra State Department of Agriculture recommendations *i.e.* Zn: 5 %, Fe: 2 %, Mn: 1 %, B: 1.0 % and Cu: 0.5 %. The foliar micronutrient formulation chelation's were made *viz.*, Grade-II (a) with EDTA, Grade-II (b) with glycine, Grade-II (c) with EDTA and Grade-II (d) with citric acid was prepared as Zn: 4 %, Fe: 3%, Mn: 1%, B: 0.5 %, Cu: 0.2 % and Mo: 0.1% and Grade-II (e) with EDTA was prepared which contains Zn: 4.5 %, Fe:3.5 %, Mn: 1 %, B: 0.5 %, Cu: 0.2 % and Mo: 0.1 %. These mixtures were prepared in the laboratory by using laboratory chemicals *viz.*, ferrous sulphate, zinc sulphate, manganese sulphate, copper sulphate, boric acid, sodium tetraborate and ammonium molybdate.

Table 1: Content of soil and foliar micronutrient grades

Grade	Zn (%)	Fe (%)	Mn (%)	B (%)	Cu (%)	Mo (%)
Soil application						
Grade-I (a) and (b)	6	5	1	1	0.5	-
Govt. notified Grade-I (c)	5	2	1	1	0.5	-
Foliar application						
Grade-II (a) to (d)	4.5	3.5	1	0.5	0.2	0.1
Govt. notified Grade-II (e)	3	2.5	1	0.5	1	0.1

Sources:**Soil application (Grade-I which were prepared in 1 kg pack)**

Formulation-I	
Grade-I (a)	: ZnSO ₄ .7H ₂ O + FeSO ₄ .7H ₂ O + H ₃ BO ₃ + MnSO ₄ .H ₂ O + CuSO ₄ .5H ₂ O (Gypsum based)
Grade-I (b)	: ZnSO ₄ .7H ₂ O + FeSO ₄ .7H ₂ O + H ₃ BO ₃ + MnSO ₄ .H ₂ O + CuSO ₄ .5H ₂ O (Bentonite based)
Govt. notified Grade-I (c)	: ZnSO ₄ .7H ₂ O + FeSO ₄ .7H ₂ O + H ₃ BO ₃ + MnSO ₄ .H ₂ O + CuSO ₄ .5H ₂ O (Gypsum based)

Foliar application (Grade-II which were prepared in 1 liter capacity)

Formulation-II	
Grade-II (a)	: ZnSO ₄ .7H ₂ O + FeSO ₄ .7H ₂ O + Na ₂ B ₄ O ₇ .10H ₂ O (Borax) + MnSO ₄ .H ₂ O + CuSO ₄ .5H ₂ O + (NH ₄) ₂ MoO ₄ (Chelation with EDTA)
Grade-II (b)	: ZnSO ₄ .7H ₂ O + FeSO ₄ .7H ₂ O + H ₃ BO ₃ + MnSO ₄ .H ₂ O + CuSO ₄ .5H ₂ O + (NH ₄) ₂ MoO ₄ (Chelation with glycine)
Grade-II (c)	: ZnSO ₄ .7H ₂ O + FeSO ₄ .7H ₂ O + H ₃ BO ₃ (Boric acid) + MnSO ₄ .H ₂ O + CuSO ₄ .5H ₂ O + (NH ₄) ₂ MoO ₄ (Chelation with EDTA)
Grade-II (d)	: ZnSO ₄ .7H ₂ O + FeSO ₄ .7H ₂ O + H ₃ BO ₃ + MnSO ₄ .H ₂ O + CuSO ₄ .5H ₂ O + (NH ₄) ₂ MoO ₄ (Chelation with citric acid)
Govt. notified Grade-II (e)	: ZnSO ₄ .7H ₂ O + FeSO ₄ .7H ₂ O + H ₃ BO ₃ + MnSO ₄ .H ₂ O + CuSO ₄ .5H ₂ O + (NH ₄) ₂ MoO ₄ (Chelation with EDTA)

Table 2: Sources used for soil and foliar micronutrient formulation

Sr. No.	Nutrient	Source	Nutrient content (%)
1	Fe	FeSO ₄ .7H ₂ O	20.10
2.	Mn	MnSO ₄ .H ₂ O	32.51
3.	Zn	ZnSO ₄ .7H ₂ O	22.75
4.	Cu	CuSO ₄ .5H ₂ O	25.47
5.	B	H ₃ BO ₃	17.49
6.	B	Na ₂ B ₄ O ₇ .10H ₂ O	11.34
7.	Mo	(NH ₄) ₂ MoO ₄	54.35

For isolation of bacteria, fungi and actinomycetes from soil three different media were used for specific group of micro flora. Soil microbial count was estimated using serial dilution method as described by Pramer and Schmidt (1964). Serial dilution plate technique is one of the most popular methods for isolation and enumeration of soil fungi, actinomycetes and bacteria (Dhingra and Sinclair, 1993). Transferred 1 g of soil sample in 10 ml of sterile distilled water in test tube (1:10). Transferred 1 ml suspension from this test tube to another tube containing 9 ml of sterile distilled water (1:100) again transfer 1 ml of suspension from this test tube to test tube containing 9 ml sterile distilled water (1:1000). Similarly, the dilution process is continued as per requirement for bacteria 10^{-7} ; fungal 10^{-4} ; for actinomycetes 10^{-5} . The concerned diluted samples were poured at the rate of 1 ml/plate. The respective melted medium (cool to 45°) was poured at rate of 20 ml/plate. Spread the medium by an inclined rotary motion of the plate. After solidification of medium, these plates were incubated at $30 \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$. Dehydrogenase enzyme activity of soil was determined by 2,3,5-Triphenyl Tetrazolium Chloride (TTC) method as described by Klein *et. al.* (1971). One gram of soil was incubated for 24 hr at $28 \pm 0.5^{\circ}\text{C}$ in 0.2 ml of a 3% TTC solution (3 g TTC in 10 ml distilled water) and 0.5 ml of 1% glucose solution. The sample was then blended with 10 ml of methanol and shaken for 30 min at 250 rpm. Allow to stand for 6h. The optical density of the red colour extract supernatant was measured at 485 nm using UV-Vis spectrophotometer. Soil dehydrogenase activity was expressed as $\mu\text{g TPF g}^{-1}$ of soil 24hr^{-1} . Acid and Alkaline phosphatase activity was measured spectrophotometrically as described by Tabatabai and Bremnar (1969). One g soil was placed in a 50 ml Erlenmeyer flask and treated with 0.25 ml of toluene and 4 ml MUB buffer (pH 6.5 and 11) and 1 ml of p-nitro phenolphosphate solution made in same buffer. After that the flask contents were mixed and incubated for 1 hr at 37°C . Later 1hr of incubation 1 ml of CaCl_2 (0.5 M) and 4 ml of NaOH (0.5 M) were added to the flask. The

coloured soil suspension was filtered through Whatman no.2 filter paper and absorbance of 64 filtrate was measured at 400 nm. The phosphatase activity was expressed as $\mu\text{g p-Nitrophenol g}^{-1}$ of soil h^{-1} .

Result and discussion

Microbial population

Microbial population in soil at harvest stage of french bean was increased significantly with different micro-nutrient grades (fig.1). Significantly higher microbial count of bacteria ($41.73 \text{ CFU} \times 10^{-7}$), fungi ($6.55 \text{ CFU} \times 10^{-4}$) and actinomycetes ($43.43 \text{ CFU} \times 10^{-5}$) at harvest stage of crop were recorded with treatment RDF+ Grade-I (a) @ 25 kg ha^{-1} (Gypsum based) which was followed by treatment RDF+ Govt. notified Grade-I (c) @ 25 kg ha^{-1} (Gypsum based) noted $38.37 \text{ CFU} \times 10^{-7}$, $5.53 \text{ CFU} \times 10^{-5}$ fungi and $40.20 \text{ CFU} \times 10^{-5}$ bacteria, fungi and actinomycetes, respectively. However, significantly lower microbial population in soil recorded with absolute control $28.52 \text{ CFU} \times 10^{-7}$, $3.93 \text{ CFU} \times 10^{-5}$ and $40.20 \text{ CFU} \times 10^{-5}$ bacteria, fungi and actinomycetes, respectively.

The application of RDF and micro-nutrient grades enhances nutrient availability and root exudation, creating a favourable environment for bacterial growth. Micronutrients also stimulate microbial enzyme activity, leading to an increase in soil microbial population in the rhizosphere of french bean. Our results are similar with findings of Narkhede *et al.* (2017), Zodge *et al.* (2019) and Bairwa *et al.* (2021).

Soil enzymes

The data referred to soil enzymes *i.e.* dehydrogenase activity, acid phosphatase activity and alkaline phosphatase activity was affected significantly by application of different micronutrient grades (fig. 2).

Significantly higher dehydrogenase activity with value $48.12 \text{ g TPF } 24\text{hr}^{-1} \text{ g}^{-1}$ soil, acid phosphatase activity in soil $53.11 \text{ g p-NP g}^{-1}$ soil hr^{-1} and alkaline phosphatase activity $65.49 \text{ g p-NP g}^{-1}$ soil hr^{-1} in soil was noted with in treatment RDF+ Grade-I (a) @ 25 kg ha^{-1}

(Gypsum based) which was followed by treatment RDF+ Govt. notified Grade-I (c) @ 25 kg ha⁻¹ (Gypsum based) *i.e.* 44.37 g TPF 24h⁻¹ g⁻¹ soil dehydrogenase activity, 51.97 g p-NP g⁻¹ soil hr⁻¹ acid phosphatase activity and 64.98 g p-NP g⁻¹ soil hr⁻¹ alkaline phosphatase activity. Whereas, significantly lower dehydrogenase activity, acid phosphatase activity and alkaline phosphatase activity in soil was noted with absolute control *i.e.* 39.19 g TPF 24h⁻¹ g⁻¹ soil, 41.84 g p-NP g⁻¹ soil hr⁻¹ and 50.84 g p-NP g⁻¹ soil hr⁻¹ respectively. The application of RDF and micronutrients improve soil fertility and plant growth, which in turn increases organic matter inputs (root exudates, decaying plant material). These organic materials serve as energy sources for soil microbes, boosting microbial biomass and thus dehydrogenase activity. Balanced fertilization and micronutrients improve the soil microbial environment, stimulating fungi and bacteria that secrete acid phosphatases. Micronutrients like Zn, Fe and Mn act as cofactors or activators of many enzymes, including phosphatases. Their presence enhances the biosynthesis and functionality of phosphatase enzymes in microbial and plant systems. The experimental findings were consistent with Apoorva *et al.* (2018), Khandare *et al.* (2019), Katkar *et al.* (2011) and Ingle *et al.* (2014).

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Fig. 1 Effect of different micronutrient grades on soil microbial population after harvest of french bean

Fig. 2 Effect of different micronutrient grades on dehydrogenase enzyme activity after harvest of french bean

Fig. 3 Effect of different micronutrient grades on acid and alkaline phosphatase activity after harvest of french bean